

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Humadi**FIRST NAME:** Samer**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Concerning the introduction of an essay, please select the incorrect answer from the following statements.**

- Answer the study question with a thesis statement.
- The introduction moves from specific to general subject.¹**
- Open with short orientation to introduce the subject.
- Provide summary or ‘road map’ for the essay.

2. **The body of an essay consists of paragraphs. The body is where you cannot make the following actions.**

- Answer the question by developing discussion.
- Offer exposition and evidence to develop discussion.
- You can refer to future directions for research.²**

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: EUCLID University, 2019), 3. .

- Use relevant examples and authoritative quotes.
3. **Please select the correct answer from the following statements.**
- You should not introduce new information in conclusions.**³
- You can introduce new information in conclusions.
- You should not restate your answer to the question.
- You cannot re-summarize the main information in conclusions.
4. **Please select the correct answer from the following statements on plagiarism and citation.**
- Plagiarism involves the use of source information without giving credit to the author.**⁴
- Use quotation marks for citations longer than four lines.
- To paraphrase, your writing style should be the same to the author's style.
- You need to cite common knowledge statements.

² Ibid.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ibid., 5.

5. Please select the correct answer from the following statements on schools of paradigms.

- Positivism.**⁵
- Focus group discussion.
- Case studies.
- Stratified sampling technique.

6. Please select the correct answer from the following statements on Qualitative sampling methods.

- Simple random samples
- Pragmatism.
- Cluster sampling
- Snowball.**⁶

7. Concerning citation styles. Please select the correct answer(s) from the following statements.

- They share the same aim in giving readers the information to identify and find a source.**⁷
- Elements included are the same.
- Formats of the elements included are the same.

⁵ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Inc, 2008), 8.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 80.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2008), 137.

- Readers should not expect you to use the citation style appropriate to their field.
8. **Please select the correct answer from the following statements on quantitative studies.**
- Used to examine cause and effect relationship between variables.⁸**
- They are subjective.
- Used to explore and discover ideas in the ongoing processes.
- Utilizes words and pictures as elements for analysis.
9. **Please select the correct answer from the following statements on qualitative studies.**
- Utilizes group discussion and in-depth interviews.⁹**
- To measure the incidence of various views and opinions in a chosen sample.
- Findings are conclusive.
- It is result oriented.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 10.

⁹ Ibid.

10. Please select the correct answer(s) from the following statements on the in-text citation used by the World Health Organization.

- Numerical.¹⁰
- Chicago author-date.
- American Psychological Association (ASA).
- Modern Language Association (MLA).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Euclid University. *ACA-401D Coursepack, Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2019.

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¹⁰ World Health Organization, *Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 2004), 24.